

Influence of Social Classroom Climate on Students Attitude to Learning in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the influence of social classroom climate on students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study was guided by two objectives from which two research questions and two hypotheses were derived. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 27,082 students in the 37 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 728 respondents. This figure was determined using Taro Yamene's formula. We have 394 students and 334 teachers. The multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample of the study. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Influence of Social Classroom Climate on Students' Attitude to Learning Questionnaire". The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools to a high extent. The researcher recommends among others that, to ensure conducive social climate that would promote positive attitude to learning, educational managers should organize periodic training for teachers on how to overcome negative effect of anti-social behaviour which.

Keywords: Classroom Climate, Attitude, Learning. Senior Secondary School.

Introduction

Provision of quality education is a priority that every country will aspire to include amongst the national goals of education. According to Kimani, Kara and Njagi (2013), the purpose of education is to equip the citizenry with values, skills and knowledge to reshape their society and eliminate inequality. This is because education helps to develop human beings physically, mentally, socially, morally and technologically to enable them function effectively in any society. It is in view of this that the National Educational goals were built on: the inculcation of national consciousness and unity; inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and the Nigeria society; the training of the mind in the understanding of the world around and the acquisition of appropriate skills and development of mental, physical, social abilities and competencies as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute meaningfully to the development of the society (NPE, 2004). The school is the institution saddled with the responsibility of providing formal education at various levels (primary, secondary and tertiary) in Nigeria and other parts of the world.

The aim of secondary education in Nigeria is to equip learners with quality education in all fields of life including vocational and special skills that can equip them to be self-reliant in decision making and to effectively pursue tertiary education (FRN, 2013). It is however worrisome that these aims are not met due to factors such as poor school infrastructures, underfunding of schools and poor school climate among others (Ehusani, 2003).

The effectiveness of a school is measured by the quality of students it produces. The quality of students produced is also determined by their attitude towards learning. For most teachers, a good student is the one who is eager to learn and has positive attitudes towards learning. Burke and Williams (2018) in a study they conducted found out that the students who are much better motivated for learning both get more successful and tend towards the thinking skills. However, concerns have been raised in recent times among teachers and other educationists about the declining interest in learning among students in secondary schools in Nigeria. Kkanal (2017) supported this view when they observed that students tend to lose interest and motivation in high school for many reasons, including feeling that they are not in a supportive environment, feeling that they are just going through the motions, or simply feeling burnt out from everything they are doing in their busy lives. This as expected affects students' attitude towards learning.

Different researchers have defined attitude towards learning in different ways. Attitude towards learning can be seen as a positive or negative predisposition towards classroom learning and every activity in the school environment, which could be cognitive, emotional, or behavioural (Bernstein, Penner, Clarke-Stewart & Roy, 2016). Attitude towards schooling has also been

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conceptualized as the way a person perceives his/her school attendance (Pezzaglia, Tressoildi, &Toso, 2019). Similarly, Veresova and Mala (2016) submitted that attitude towards learning can be understood as beliefs, thoughts and opinions about schools and learning in it, emotions and a relationship towards school and learning built upon feelings, and a tendency to behave in accordance with favourable and unfavourable experiences with school and learning.

According to Kpolovie, Joe, and Okoto (2010), students develop good sense of belonging and engagement in learning only when they have a positive attitude towards learning. The condition of belonging means that a student is a valued member of the classroom and school community while still maintaining his or her uniqueness. Some students view schooling as essential to their long-term wellbeing, and this attitude is reflected in their participation in academic and non-academic activities. Students tend to have good relations with school staff and with other students when their attitude to learning is positive. A number of factors could determine a student's attitude to learning and one of these is the classroom climate.

Classroom climate according to Chamberlin in Koko, Okon, Essien and Martin (2009) is a subtle spirit that exists in a school, both in the minds of the teachers and students and in every act, which may never be exactly described or analysed, but which an experienced observer recognizes when he enters a school. Similarly, Ambrose, Bridges, DiPietro and Lovett (2010) defined classroom or learning climate as the "intellectual, social, emotional, and physical environments in which our students learn." Biemen (2011) described classroom climate as the classroom environment, the social climate, the emotional and the physical aspects of the classroom. It's the idea that teachers influence student growth and behaviour. The student's behaviour affects peer interaction the responsibility of influencing these behaviours is placed with the instructor. The way the instructor organizes the classroom should lead to a positive environment rather than a destructive and/or an environment that is not conducive to learning.

Classroom climate involves areas of discipline, administration, student-student relationship, student-teacher relationship and academic dimensions. Gammage and Rogers in Koko, Okon, Essien and Martin (2009) identified aspects of classroom climate to include the physical appearance and layout of the classroom, the hidden curriculum, communication, instructional materials, mutual respect and rapport, standard of work expected by the teacher among others.

Classroom climate comprises the physical, psychological, social, emotional and technological climate of the classroom. The physical climate is all about the design of a classroom, including how it's laid out to influence learning, and which spaces are designated for learning activities. This can include the furniture that's used to fill the space and even the equipment a teacher relies on to enhance the learning experience (Western Governors University, 2021).

Physical classroom climate also refers to the way a classroom is set up, right from the accessibility and visibility that it offers to the distractibility that it can avoid. It pertains to everything from the way the materials in the room are arranged to how easily each student can see the board, projection screen, teachers and the likes. Taking care of all these aspects in classroom ensures a positive physical environment where students can concentrate on their studies, without failing for any kind of distraction (Gurukul School, 2019).

Furthermore, the social classroom climate has to do with the interpersonal relationships, modes of communication between individuals, and other group processes that exist in the context of a classroom (Dörnyei & Murphey, 2015). A growing body of evidence suggests that the classroom social climate plays a significant role in what actually happens in the process of learning, and the way that the people in the classroom group think and behave (Jennings & Greenberg, 2019). In the same vein, Klem and Connell (2014) noted that the social aspect of classroom climate refers to relationships between students (e.g., individualistic vs. team-oriented, or competitive vs. cooperative) and between students and instructor (e.g., the instructor being approachable or authoritative to students) and the social atmosphere of the class (e.g., casual, formal, democratic, inclusive).

However, creating an ideal classroom climate ought to be a priority of every concerned teacher or educationist and this takes cognizance of a number of factors which include temperature, lighting, and noise control etc (Murugan & Rajoo, 2013). The extent to which students' learning could be enhanced depends on their location within the school compound, the structure of their classroom, availability of instructional facilities and others. It is believed that a school with conducive classroom climate contributes to stir up expected outcomes of learning that will facilitate good academic performance, by encouraging effective teaching and learning (Duruji, 2014).

Several research has been conducted on classroom learning environment around the world to look at disciplinary attitudes, achievement, teacher practices, and program evaluation (Lim & Fraser, 2018). both theoretical (Bourdieu, 16) and empirical (Lucas, 2020) research identify positive classroom learning environment as essential for supporting students effective learning and their positive perception of themselves as learners. In a large scale study of middle school students, without sub-analysis by language status, Fraser and Kahle (2017) found that although classroom, home and peer environment significantly contributed to student's attitudes toward mathematics and science, only classroom environment significantly predicted achievement. In a meta-analysis of 119 studies conducted across a range of educational but with no sub-analysis by language status, Cornelius-White (2017) found strong associations between classroom environments and student social and academic outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

The influence of classroom climate on student's attitude to learning cannot be overemphasized. Secondary schools in Nigeria are set up with the objective of preparing young people for higher education and to pursue other vocation or career path. This makes this level of education very important because it determines the quality of workforce that will be released to man various sectors of the economy. Unfortunately, it has been observed that there is declining interest of students towards schooling and worst still is the observed poor attitude to learning among most students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This has led to increasing cases of cultism and other juvenile delinquencies in public secondary. The reported poor performance of students in the West African Senior Secondary Examination is a testament of this fact (Adeyemi, 2021).

This poor learning attitude of students have been attributed to a number of factors as seen in several studies carried out by other researchers. Some have attributed it to poor funding of public schools, shortage of teachers and so on. Not much has been done in ascertaining how classroom climate affects students' attitude to learning. Consequently, there is a dearth of literature in this area. The question then is could the classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis? Providing answers to this question is the task of this study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the extent to which social classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the extent to which students classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Find out the extent to which physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does social classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female students on the extent to which social classroom climate influences students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of of male and female students on the extent to which physical classroom climate influences students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a population of 27,082 students in the 37 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 728 respondents comprising 394 students and 334 teachers in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula. The multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample of the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire titled "Influence of Classroom Climate on Students' Attitude to Learning Questionnaire". The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypotheses accepted when the computed value was greater than the critical value at the significance level of 0.05. On the contrary, the null hypothesis was also accepted and the alternate hypotheses rejected when +the computed value is less than the critical table value.

Result

Research Question 1: To what extent does social classroom climate influence students’ attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis on the extent social classroom climate influence students’ attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools

S/N.	Items	Male Students (384)			Female Students (326)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Decision	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Teachers’ friendliness to students’ influences their understanding of what is taught.	2.56	0.80	High Extent	2.55	0.80	High Extent
2.	Students find learning more interesting when there is collaboration among them while learning.	2.95	0.86	High Extent	2.75	0.83	High Extent
3.	Learners are willing to contribute to class discussions when the teacher motivates them to do so.	2.80	0.84	High Extent	2.85	0.84	High Extent
4.	Learners are more willing to participate in classroom activities when they are not laughed at or insulted for making mistakes.	2.65	0.81	High Extent	2.90	0.85	High Extent
5.	Maintaining mutual respect between teachers and students makes learners learn better.	2.75	0.83	High Extent	2.60	0.81	High Extent
6.	Having a hostile classroom climate creates anxiety in learners which affects their learning.	3.00	0.87	High Extent	2.80	0.84	High Extent
7.	Engaging students in periodic fun activities in the classroom encourages participation of all learners in learning activities	2.85	0.84	High Extent	2.95	0.86	High Extent
	Grand Mean	2.79	0.83		2.77	0.83	

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 1 above revealed the position of students on the extent to which social classroom climate influence students’ attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Majority of the respondents agreed with all the items in the table. The grand mean scores of 2.79, 2.77 and standard deviation scores of 0.83 and 0.83 for students and teachers respectively indicate their view that social classroom climate influence students’ attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent. The answer to research question 1 therefore is that: student and teachers indicate that social classroom climate influence student’s attitude to learning to a high extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent does physical classroom climate influence students’ attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis on the extent Physical Classroom Climate Influence Students’ Attitude to Learning in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N.	Items	Male Students (384)			Female Students (326)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Decision	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
8.	Students find it difficult to concentrate when a class is stuffy and not well ventilated.	2.95	0.86	High Extent	2.55	0.80	High Extent
9.	Students are less interested in learning when the classroom lacks adequate chairs.	2.60	0.81	High Extent	2.70	0.82	High Extent
10.	Students who are exposed to laboratory practical are more willing to learn science based subjects.	2.55	0.80	High Extent	2.90	0.85	High Extent
11.	Availability of library facilities in your school makes students willing to engage in self-study outside the classroom.	2.80	0.84	High Extent	2.60	0.81	High Extent
12.	Availability of football pitch makes students show interest in physical education subjects.	2.75	0.83	High Extent	2.80	0.84	High Extent
13.	Availability of mock up instructional materials arouses students’ interest in learning.	2.90	0.85	High Extent	2.95	0.86	High Extent

14.	Availability of pictures as instructional materials enhances learners' retention of what they are taught.	2.55	0.80	High	2.50	0.79	High
				Extent			Extent
	Grand Scores	2.72	0.82		2.71	0.82	

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2 above revealed the position of teachers and students on the extent to which physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Majority of the respondents agreed with all the items in the table. The grand mean scores of 2.72, 2.71 and standard deviation scores of 0.82 and 0.81 for students respectively indicate their view that physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent. The answer to research question 2 therefore is that: students and teachers indicates that physical classroom climate influence students attitude to learning to a high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female students on the extent to which social classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: Z-test Analysis of Difference in the Mean Ratings of Male and Female Students on the Extent to which Social Classroom Climate Influence Students' Attitude to Learning in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Category of Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Students	3842.79	0.83	0.24	± 1.96		Ho
Teachers	3262.77	0.83				Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

From Table 3 above, the calculated z-value of 0.24 is less than the z-critical value of 1.96 Given the above, the null hypothesis 1 which states that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent to which social classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is hereby accepted. The

implication of this is that students consented that social classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female students on the extent to which physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis of Difference in the Mean Ratings of Male and Female Students on the Extent Physical Classroom Climate Influence Students' Attitude to Learning in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Category of Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Students	384	2.72	0.82	-1.17	±1.96	Ho
Teachers	326	2.71	0.81			Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

From Table 4 above, the calculated z-value of -1.17 is less than the z-critical value of 1.96. Given the above, the null hypothesis 2 which states that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent to which physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is hereby accepted. The implication of this is that students agreed that physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the findings of the study for research question one revealed that social classroom climate as an aspect of classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis to a high extent. With grand mean scores of 2.79 and 2.77 which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. The corresponding hypothesis one also revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent to which social classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. This finding is in line with Bilbo (2022), who viewed social classroom climate as the type of environment that is created for students by the school, teachers, and peers. Teachers are continually looking to create a "positive" social classroom climate in which student learning is maximized. He further mentioned that it involves having an

environment where students feel safe, nurtured, and intellectually stimulated. This type of positive classroom climate allows students to meet their basic needs of physical and mental health. Also, Hamre and Pianta (2015), supported that positive social classroom climates characterized by supportive teacher-child relationships and interactions have been shown to influence students' psychosocial adjustment in preschool and later grades and to improve student's social competencies with peers. This is especially important as students' abilities to relate well to peers are especially important for adaptive school functioning and adjustment, as it has been shown to be an especially important area of social growth (Pianta, 2018). Howes, Phillips, and Whitebrook, (2022), further noted that the development of children's social competencies is associated with a positive classroom environment and teachers who provide a nurturing context for positive peer interactions.

The findings of the study for research question two revealed that physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis to a very high extent. With grand mean scores of 2.72 and 2.71 which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. The corresponding hypothesis two also revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent to which physical classroom climate influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt. This finding is in line with the view of Oluchukwu (2020), who mentioned that the physical classroom climate is a very important component in the school systems. This include the classrooms, libraries, technical workshops, laboratories, teachers' quality, school management, teaching methods, peers and so on, are variables that affect students' academic achievement Hence, the school environment remains an important area that should be studied and well managed to enhance students' attitude towards the learning. Also, the quality of education not only depends on the teachers as reflected in the performance of their duties, but also in the effective coordination of the school environment (Ajao, 2021). Furthermore, Ijeoma (2017), states that a conducive learning environment can have effect on both the attitude and achievement of students. She also observes that overcrowded classrooms are now a permanent feature of academic settings at all levels of the education system. Teacher net (2018) also observes that the surroundings in which students learn can greatly influence their academic performance and well-being.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that classroom climate that influence students' attitude to learning in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis include social classroom climate, physical classroom climate and psychological classroom climate. The study further concluded that teachers' friendliness to students influence their understanding of what is

taught, poor facilities such as stuffy classrooms, inadequate chairs, sports facility and other instructional materials makes it difficult for students to learn.

Implication for Counselling

The following implications for counselling were made:

- i. **School teachers should ensure that, a class room must have a positive climate.** The children must feel a sense of security. The atmosphere must be conducive to taking safe challenges without fear of ridicule. A positive environment is the building block in developing a child with the positive self-efficacy to take safe challenges. If a child fears shame and ridicule from peers and teachers, they will avoid taking risks to protect themselves from embarrassment.
- ii. **Teachers must take their position as a role model seriously in the school.** A major factor in the learning environment is the teacher's role. Through observing role models, children learn skills that will assist their successful assimilation into society. A class room that lacks a teacher that exhibits quiet control will see behavioral issues exacerbate. The learning environment will dictate how well or poorly a child will learn.
- iii. **Teachers must learn to be accommodating and friendly to students.** Children learn from educators and educators learn from the students. Observing the students can result in squelching bad behaviors before they become issues. Accommodating and restructuring of the class room environment can squelch further outbursts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. To ensure conducive social climate that would promote positive attitude to learning, educational managers should organize periodic training for teachers on the negative effect of anti-social behaviour which will ensure that students are treated with care, fairness and consistency.
2. School administrators and managers should ensure that the physical classroom learning environment is improved by renovating and repainting old and dilapidated classroom buildings to make them more attractive and conducive for teaching and learning activities. This will improve students' attitude to learning.
3. The Post primary schools board should organize periodic training for teachers in public secondary schools on how to maintain positive psychological climate in their classrooms as this will improve students' attitude to learning and their academic performance.

REFERENCES

Açıkgoz, U. K. (2017). *Effective learning and teaching*. (7th.ed.). Bilis Publishing

Açıkgoz, U. K. (2017). *Active Learning*. (9th.ed.). Bilis Publishing.

Ambrose, S. A., Bridges, M. W., DiPietro, M. & Lovett, M. C. (2020). *Classroom Climate*. Retrieved from https://teaching.cornell.edu/teaching-resources/assessment_evaluation/inclusion-accessibility-accommodation/building-inclusive-0

Baker, M. L., Sigmon, J. N. & Nugent, M. E. (2021). Truancy reduction: Keeping students in school. (Report No. NCJ-188947). Rockville, MD: *National Criminal Justice Reference Service*. Retrieved from <https://www.ncjrs.gov/pdffiles1/ojdp/188947.pdf>.

Bernstein, D. A., Penner, L. A., Clarke- Stewart, A. & Roy, E.J. (2016). *Psychology* (7th Edition). Boston: Houghton Mifflin.

Bierman, K. L. (2021). "The promise and potential of studying the "invisible hand" of teacher influence on peer relations and student outcomes: A commentary". *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*. SI Teachers and Classroom Social Dynamics. 32 (5):297–303. doi: 10.1016/j.appdev.2011.04.004.

Bourdieu, P. (1986). The forms of capital. In J.G. Richardson (Ed). *Handbook of theory and research for the sociology of education* (pp.241_258) Westport Greenwood Press.

Burke, L. & Joanne M. Williams (2008). Developing young thinkers: An intervention aimed to enhance children's thinking skills. *Thinking Skills and Creativity* v. 3, (pp.104- 124).

Colhando, S. (2020). Importance of Developing a Learning Attitude. Retrieved from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-developing-learning-attitude-sandra-colhando->

Cornelius-White, J. (2017). Learner-centered teacher-student relationships are effective: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 77,113_143

Dörnyei, Z. and Murphy, G. (2015) *The psychology of the language learner revisited*.

Duruji, M. M., Azuh, D. & Oviasogie, F. (2014). Learning environment and academic performance of secondary school students in external examinations: A study of selected schools in Ota,

Nigeria. Proceedings of EDULEARN 14 Conferences, Barcelona, Spain. 7th-9th July, PP. 5042-5053. Accessed 23/10/19 from: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper//20ec786278f31b430d0feee79dfc274949fb483b>

Fraser, B.J. & Kahle, J.B. (2017). Classroom, home and peer environment influences on student outcomes in science and mathematics: An analysis of systemic reform data. *International Journal of Science Education*, 29(15).1891_1909.

Gurukul School (2019) Physical environment of a classrooms play a crucial role in ensuring engrossed learning. Retrieved from <https://gurukultheschool.com/blog/physical-environment-of-classrooms-play-a-crucial-role-in-ensuring-engrossed-learning/#:~:text=The%20term%20physical%20environment%20of,distractibility%20that%20it%20can%20avoid.>

Hamre, B. K., & Pianta, R. C. (2021). *Early teacher–child relationships and the trajectory of children’s school outcomes through eighth grade*. *Child Development*, 72, 625–638. doi:10.1111/1467-8624.00301

Hamre, B. K. & Pianta, R. C. (2017). Learning opportunities in preschool and early elementary classrooms. In R. C. Pianta, M. J. Cox, & K. L. Snow (Eds.), *School readiness and the transition to kindergarten in the era of accountability* (pp. 49–83). *Baltimore, MD: Brookes*.

Hong, Y., Li, X., Fang, X., Zhao, G., Zhao, J., Zhao, Q. (2021). *Care arrangements of AIDS orphans and their relationship with children’s psychosocial well-being in rural China*. *Health Policy Plan*. 26, 115–123. doi: 10.1093/heapol/czq025

Jennings, P. and Greenberg, A. (2019) *The prosocial classroom: Teacher social and emotional competence in relation to student and classroom outcomes* *Review of Educational Research*

Khanal, S. P. (2017) *Psychological Examination*. Chicago: Jupital Publication.

Klem, A. & Connel, D. (2014) Relationships matter: linking teacher support to student engagement and achievement. *Journal of School Health*. 2(3) 56-67

Koko, E., Okon, A.E., Essien, E.E. and Martin, I.M. (2019) Classroom Climate and Students’ Academic Achievement in Social Studies in Cross River, Nigeria. *An International*

Multi-Disciplinary Journal, Ethiopia 3 (4) 413-428

Kpolovie, P. J., Joe, A. I., & Okoto, T. (2014). Academic achievement prediction: role of interest in learning and attitude towards school. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education (IJHSSE)*, 1(11), 73-100.

Lim, C.T.D & Fraser B.J. (2018). Learning environments research in English classrooms. *Learning Environment Research*, 21(3),435_449.

Lucas T., Henze, R., & Donato, R. (2020). Promoting the success of Latin language minority students: An exploratory study of six high schools. *Harvard Educational Review*, 60(3) 315_341.

Malaysia. Organized by worldconferences.net. Accessed 22/11/19 from <https://worldconferences.net/proceedings/icssr2013/toc/218%20%20murugan%20->

Murugan, A. & Rajoo, L. (2013). Students' perceptions of mathematics classroom environment & mathematics achievement: *A Study in Sipitang, Sabah, Malaysia: Proceeding of the International Conference on Social Science Research, ICSSR 2013. 4-5 June 2013, Penang*,

Orluchukwu, C. (2013). Environmental influence on academic performance of secondary school students in Port Harcourt local government area of Rivers State. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4(12), 34-38.

Osuji, C.U. Wey-Amaewhule, B. & Akide, E. (2023). *Influence of Classroom Climate on Students' Attitude to Learning in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt* The learning environment will dictate how well or poorly a child will learn. *Metropolis. International Journal of Advanced Research and Learning*, 2 (2) 34-48

Veresova, M., & Mala, D. (2016). Attitude towards school and academic achievement of adolescents. *European Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences*. 11(90), 870-876.